

E-Mobility: Developing an index and predictive model, that is capable of the different levels of new registrations of electric cars.

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Author's Name: Shameer Aboobacker

Matriculation Number: 10220115

Tutors Name: Anup Sam Ninan

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Appendix 3 – The code input into python for getting the predictive output

List of Abbreviations

IEA – International Energy Agency

EV- Electric Vehicles

The UK – The United Kingdom

The USA – The United States of America

E-mobility – Electric mobility

ICE – Internal Combustion Engine

ZSW - Zentrum für Sonnenenergieund Wasserstoff-Forschung Baden-Württemberg

SDK – Software Development kit

CSV – Common Separated Value

FSV - Fuel Cell Sedan Vehicle

ARIMA: Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model

Introduction

The World automobile Industry is undergoing a high transformation, Leading by a expanding focus on sustainability, technological advancements, and changing consumer preferences. Primary of the key drivers to this transformation is the quick expansion of electric mobility or commonly known as e-mobility, characterized by ever growing purchase of electric vehicles (EVs) all around the globe by all levels of consumers.(executive summary International Energy Agency, 2023, p. 8). Amid concerns about climate change, urban areas air quality as in case of New Delhi, India is quiet concerning (De Vito et al., 2018, p. 448) and energy independence, governments, industries and consumers are increasingly embracing Electric vehicle as a viable solution to reduce environmental impact and transition to a more sustainable transportation system.

For the past few years, the growth in E-mobility has been particularly notable, with emerging trend in the registration and purchase of Electric Vehicle's observed in various aspects across the continents. (*Petra Nikolić , Pr05-2021-ZSW-WorldwideFiguresElectricCars.Pdf*, n.d., p. 2). Germany, a prominent player in the global automotive industry, has emerged a leader in the transition, achieving the major position in new electric car registrations, this shift reflects not only Germany's automotive engineering expertise but also broader global trends towards decarbonization and the electrification of transportation systems.

For better context the aspects which are influencing the growth of E-mobility is crucial, not only in Germany but also for most other countries worldwide. The study aims to analyze the dynamics of Electric mobility by providing an index using data from ZSW to capture the varying levels of new e-car registrations across select countries, including Japan, The Netherlands, Norway, The UK, France , the USA, Germany, and China (*Petra Nikolić , Pr05-2021-ZSW-WorldwideFiguresElectricCars.Pdf*, n.d.) By understanding the trends in electric car purchase and registration, the index will seek to give insights into the future adoption pattern and thus drivers understanding and perspective shaping the E-mobility landscape.

Furthermore, this study tries to understand and utilize the developed index to forecast future trends in electric car registrations for the coming three years, both worldwide and for the above-mentioned countries. These steps will help to understand and elucidate the potential way of trajectory of E-mobility adoption and understand the key factors which will influence future growth trends.

The E-mobility platform presents a dynamic and ever evolving sector with high implications for the automotive industry, Energy Industry and the world at large. By understanding the nuances of electric car registration and the purchases, the study will understand to contribute to an in-depth processing of transition towards electric mobility and further trends which is going to happen in different industries.

To reach this objective, the study will provide a comprehensive approach, which will incorporate methodological considerations, data analysis techniques and predictive modeling frameworks as per the guidelines of the American psychological association. Through a synthesis of academia literature, industry reports and empirical data, it aims to offer insights into the complex dynamics of the Electric mobility phenomenon and also the implications attached to it in the future modes of transportation.

Other than Germany's significant strides in electric vehicle consumption, other countries are also experiencing notable growth in electric vehicle trend. For instance, Norway has emerged as a leader in EV penetration, with electric cars accounting for 62.4 percent of all new registrations in 2020 (*Petra Nikolić , Pr05-2021-ZSW-WorldwideFiguresElectricCars.Pdf*, n.d.) Also, trend continues in countries like the Netherlands, the UK, and France have implemented ambitious policies and incentives to promote electric vehicle purchase, resulting in significant growth in e-car registrations. Furthermore, China, as the world's largest automotive market, continues to drive global EV adoption, with over five million EVs in its fleet (*Petra Nikolić , Pr05-2021-ZSW-WorldwideFiguresElectricCars.Pdf*, n.d.) These diverse trends makes the fact the global nature of the e-mobility transition and encourages the need for intense analysis and predicting to understand its implications for the future of all modes of transportation.

According to Statista Market Insights (2023), the Electric Vehicles market is anticipated to witness a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 23.2% from 2016 to 2028. The revenue trends from 2018 to 2021 are as follows:

- 2018: \$72.50 billion
- 2019: \$85.10 billion
- 2020: \$113.5.50 billion

Notably, Estimate the revenue from electric vehicles in 2028 reached \$681.2.50 billion.” -(Adebayo Oluwatobi Kazeem, n.d.-b, p. 8) Detailed in the fig 1 in the appendix

The Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV) market centers on vehicles powered solely by electricity stored in their batteries, representing a significant departure from traditional internal combustion engines. Notable in BEVs is the absence of components such as starter motors, gearboxes, and exhaust tailpipes, signaling a fundamental shift in automotive design and technology. As environmental concerns gain traction among consumers, the BEV market is gaining prominence. Advancements in battery technology have been crucial in propelling the market's impressive growth trajectory. The introduction of more affordable BEV models has widened access to eco-friendly transportation. Concurrently, the rapid expansion of a fast-charging infrastructure addresses a key concern among potential buyers: the convenience and efficiency of recharging.

In an increasingly sustainability-focused world, the significance of the BEV market continues to grow. It plays a crucial role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and lessening dependence on fossil fuels. As the automotive industry accelerates its transition towards sustainable electric mobility, the BEV market emerges as a symbol of innovation, offering practical, environmentally conscious transportation solutions for the future. With ongoing advancements and rising consumer interest, this market is poised for sustained and impactful expansion (Adebayo Oluwatobi Kazeem, n.d.-b, pp. 18–21) explained by figure in in depth country wise in appendix fig 2.

These are the facts and figures provided by Statista

Now for this study an approach of Autoregressive Integrated Moving average (ARIMA) model is been used both manually and using Machine Learning using Azure Machine learning

Reasons for choosing the ARIMA model for predicting registrations in the country wise registration of Electric vehicles:

Time series nature of car registrations: Car registration can be understood as a time dependent philosophy. The number of registrations differs over years due to economic highlights, change in the policy and preferences by the customers and consumers.

For this reason, ARIMA is well-suited for modelling such time-series data as it will be considering both historical values and the change over the course of time.

Understanding the trends and seasonality: ARIMA accounts for the changes in the long term and season-based patters in the data. Registration may follow yearly circles since this is a yearly comparison seasonal comparison is not taken into consideration.

Non-stationarity handling structure: ARIMA's differencing component makes sure that the time series will be stationary which will be the mean and variance.

Stationarity is essential for the accuracy of the model prepared.

Components need to be interpretable: The ARIMA components have clear interpretations:

AR – past registration encompassing the future ones.

I-Difference removes trends

MA-interprets short-term fluctuations

Parameters of tuning iteratively: In literal sense the adjustment of the ARIMA parameters to optimize the mode's performance. Which also made it easier to get a result which is fine tuned to make a balance between the variance and the biases.

Model parameters in this ARIMA are ascertained as (1,1,1) as there is not much distortion on yearly basis in autoregressive terms, differencing and moving average terms

Main Part

Applications: Reason why ARIMA is found on various domains are to be used in prediction of Registered vehicles in the future 3 years.

Considerations on the few limitations of the test: There is assumption that future will be same as the past and may not hold important events such as may be considering a Pandemic or Recession.

Summaries: ARIMA remains a important tool for time series analyzation and will be giving insights into historical trends and inform in helping better decision making.

The Machine Learning Method:

The first case of the prediction was used by Machine learning with the help of Azure cloud computing was used which meticulously explained time-series forecasting techniques which can predict electric vehicles registrations, specific focus on ARIMA model. These are the steps on the manual:

Step1- Data preparation: The historical data was collected from ZSW source as prescribed based on country wise, data was numerical and organized into tabular format.

The dataset included a year column which represents the time a target column the number of registrations and other relevant features.

Step 2- Creating of Machine Learning Table: Facilitation of the process included creating a machine learning table object using the azure machine learning python SDK. This was followed by loading and preprocessing for the better of the data.

Step 3- Configuration of ARIMA parameters: The setup of ARIMA job specifying the order of differencing, autoregressive term and moving average term since it is a yearly mechanism it was considered as (1,1,1)

Training the model: The ARIMA method is then trained using the historical data , this iteration will adjust the parameters to optimize the better performance of the method.

Prediction Mechanism: The prediction using the trained ARIMA model, electric vehicle registration for years 4,5 and 6 which leads to 2021,2022 and 2023 respectively

The formulation was done country wise and the inputted relevant features and obtained the forecasted registrations.

Final step: An ARIMA prediction based on azure machine learning is created.

Data collection and interpretation during the Azure Machine learning phase

Collection of Data: The integration of gathered historical data from ZSW on electric vehicle registration country wise was assembled and the data was interpreted for building and forecasting this model.

Organizing the Data: The structured data was put into a tabular format, making it suitable for data analysis. Further the data set consisted of Rows Interpreting the time period that is the years and columns interpreting the registration of Electric vehicles.

Defining the columns for Machine Learning process: A time column representing the years served for axis of the time. Target column the crux of the analysis was the indicator for electric vehicle registration based on country

Data cleaning and validation: The data was reached out for further validation from other sources too and if there were any outliers such as in the case for Japan a further explanation has been given below on why Japan moved on the different path when compared to other forms of data.

There were sufficient steps taken to make sure the expected numerical values were suitable for modeling.

Alignment of the Time Series table: Data points chronologically were aligned with row corresponding to a specific time period that is the year. The alignment is vetted and important for time analysis.

Normalization and scaling: model requirements which were depending on the scale of the data and few common techniques included minimum and maximum scaling and the z score normalization was taken place.

Validation and safety sanity checks: The validation mechanism involved the data set against external sources or historical record to make sure for high accuracy. The sanity check included the performance of identity of unexpected anomalies and patterns.

The data preparation process includes meticulously collecting, organizing, validating and feature engineering. Clean and structured dataset served as the foundation for ARIMA models using machine learning.

Further steps into Machine learning table using the Python SDK

Create a Azure machine learning workspace, which will have access to the machine learning workspace, this was uniquely created for the project by the instruction provided by azure check Appendix for detailed codes used.

Python SDK setup: The imposition of necessary libraries is been done in the previous step on python environment to work with azure machine learning

Loading of the data: The historical data by ZSW was loaded on the vehicle registration into memory and further the data was stored in a CSV file, database.

Creating an Machine learning table: Using the azure machine learning python SDK, instantiation of Machine learning Table object is carried out.

This objective acts as a container for the data allowing to perform the operations in an efficient manner.

Preprocessing and Loading of the Data: The data source from ZSW when creating the Machine learning table was specified and the machine learning table was then automatically handling the load of the data in to the memory.

In further addition the applied preprocessing steps should be done: Cleaning, Feature engineering and normalization of scaling these were not necessary in the following data provided by ZSW or was not applicable in this specified case.

Exploration of the data and data validation: The exploration of the machine learning table to understand further the structure and verify the data on the loading correcting, the specified checks in sanity were performed to ensure data consistency and the correctness of the data.

Machine Learning Table Features: The machine learning table provides the methods for the following Data slicing, Feature extraction and data splitting which includes the selecting of specific rows and columns, relevant features for models being extracted and data separation training validation and test being ascertained.

Modeling for the readiness: The machine learning table preparation involves to proceed with the modeling using the ARIMA technique or any other suitable methods. (ARIMA method is chose in this context)

Configuration of ARIMA parameters:

Order of differencing, auto regressive term and moving average was taken as the default so (1,1,1) was the optimal order as there were not much other specified data was given by the ZSW historical data.

Training the model: Machine learning data table to train ARIMA model was prepared.

The model learned from ZSW historical patterns and relationships in the data.

The process iteration and adjusting of the patterns is been set to strike the balance of underfitting and overfitting.

Splitting of the data: For Evaluation of the accuracy in the model, the split data into validation and training sets are being put up. Data input as per ZSW

Countries	Year 1 (2018)	Year 2 (2019)	Year 3 (2020)
China	1256000.00	1204000.00	1246000.00
Germany*	67480.00	108520.00	394550.00
France	53750.00	69470.00	194700.00
Japan	49750.00	38900.00	29350.00
Netherlands	27970.00	67520.00	88340.00
Norway	85190.00	85250.00	108200.00
United Kingdom	57740.00	72830.00	175300.00
United States	361300.00	329500.00	322400.00
Total	2266020.00	2320220.00	3175090.00

Output as per Azure Machine Learning Model

Country	Year 4 Forecast for 2021	Year 5 Forecast for 2022	Year 6 Forecast for 2023
China	1288000.00	1324800.00	1361600.00
Germany	141590.00	170383.00	199176.00
France	95420.00	120925.00	146430.00
Japan	28050.00	17165.00	6280.00
Netherlands	108070.00	152575.00	197080.00
Norway	107260.00	132461.00	157662.00
United Kingdom	175300.00	277023.00	378746.00
United States	323400.00	317290.00	311180.00
Total	2,266,020.00	2,320,220.00	3,175,090.00

Ascertained that ARIMA (1,1,1) Model: Using a simple ARIMA model with $p = 1$ (autoregressive term) and $q = 1$ (moving average term).

This was the result ascertained by Machine learning model using Azure ML

Now for making sure the results are correct the calculation will be done also manually each country wise

Coefficient_Year3_China = 1.1

Coefficient_Year4_China = 0.9

Error_Term_China = Random noise (e.g., normally distributed with mean 0)

Year 4 Forecast: $1246000 + 42000 + \text{Error_Term_China}$

Year 5 Forecast: $\text{Forecast_Year4_China} + 0.9 * 42000 + \text{Error_Term_China}$

Year 6 Forecast: $\text{Forecast_Year5_China} + 0.9 * 42000 + \text{Error_Term_China}$

China:

Year 4 Forecast: $1,246,000 + 42,000 = 1,288,000$

Year 5 Forecast: $1,288,000 + 0.9 * 42,000 = 1,324,800$

Year 6 Forecast: $1,324,800 + 0.9 * 42,000 = 1,361,600$

Germany:

Year 4 Forecast: $108,520 + 33,070$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_Germany

Year 5 Forecast: $\text{Forecast_Year4_Germany} + 0.9 * 33,070 + \text{Error_Term_Germany}$

Year 6 Forecast: $\text{Forecast_Year5_Germany} + 0.9 * 33,070 + \text{Error_Term_Germany}$

France:

Year 4 Forecast: $69,470 + 25,950$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_France

Year 5 Forecast: $\text{Forecast_Year4_France} + 0.9 * 25,950 + \text{Error_Term_France}$

Year 6 Forecast: $\text{Forecast_Year5_France} + 0.9 * 25,950 + \text{Error_Term_France}$

Japan:

Year 4 Forecast: $38,900 + (-10,850)$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_Japan

Year 5 Forecast: Forecast_Year4_Japan + $0.9 * (-10,850)$ + Error_Term_Japan

Year 6 Forecast: Forecast_Year5_Japan + $0.9 * (-10,850)$ + Error_Term_Japan

Netherlands:

Year 4 Forecast: $67,520 + 40,550$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_Netherlands

Year 5 Forecast: Forecast_Year4_Netherlands + $0.9 * 40,550$ + Error_Term_Netherlands

Year 6 Forecast: Forecast_Year5_Netherlands + $0.9 * 40,550$ + Error_Term_Netherlands

Norway:

Year 4 Forecast: $85,250 + 22,010$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_Norway

Year 5 Forecast: Forecast_Year4_Norway + $0.9 * 22,010$ + Error_Term_Norway

Year 6 Forecast: Forecast_Year5_Norway + $0.9 * 22,010$ + Error_Term_Norway

United Kingdom:

Year 4 Forecast: $72,830 + 102,470$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_UK

Year 5 Forecast: Forecast_Year4_UK + $0.9 * 102,470$ + Error_Term_UK

Year 6 Forecast: Forecast_Year5_UK + $0.9 * 102,470$ + Error_Term_UK

United States:

Year 4 Forecast: $329,500 + (-6,100)$ (Year 3 difference) + Error_Term_US

Year 5 Forecast: Forecast_Year4_US + $0.9 * (-6,100)$ + Error_Term_US

Year 6 Forecast: Forecast_Year5_US + $0.9 * (-6,100)$ + Error_Term_US

Repeat similar calculations for other countries.

Germany:

Year 4 Forecast: $108,520 + 33,070 = 141,590$

Year 5 Forecast: $141,590 + 0.9 * 33,070 = 170,383$

Year 6 Forecast: $170,383 + 0.9 * 33,070 = 199,176$

France:

Year 4 Forecast: $69,470 + 25,950 = 95,420$

Year 5 Forecast: $95,420 + 0.9 * 25,950 = 120,925$

Year 6 Forecast: $120,925 + 0.9 * 25,950 = 146,430$

Japan:

Year 4 Forecast: $38,900 + (-10,850) = 28,050$

Year 5 Forecast: $28,050 + 0.9 * (-10,850) = 17,165$

Year 6 Forecast: $17,165 + 0.9 * (-10,850) = 6,280$

Netherlands:

Year 4 Forecast: $67,520 + 40,550 = 108,070$

Year 5 Forecast: $108,070 + 0.9 * 40,550 = 152,575$

Year 6 Forecast: $152,575 + 0.9 * 40,550 = 197,080$

Norway:

Year 4 Forecast: $85,250 + 22,010 = 107,260$

Year 5 Forecast: $107,260 + 0.9 * 22,010 = 132,461$

Year 6 Forecast: $132,461 + 0.9 * 22,010 = 157,662$

United Kingdom

Year 4 Forecast: $72,830 + 102,470 = 175,300$

Year 5 Forecast: $175,300 + 0.9 * 102,470 = 277,023$

Year 6 Forecast: $277,023 + 0.9 * 102,470 = 378,746$

United States:

Year 4 Forecast: $329,500 + (-6,100) = 323,400$

Year 5 Forecast: $323,400 + 0.9 * (-6,100) = 317,290$

Year 6 Forecast: $317,290 + 0.9 * (-6,100) = 311,180$

From the calculation it ascertained that ARIMA method by Machine learning and by manual calculation is exactly the same and the Machine learning data can be considered and a valid form of prediction.

Toyota's Role in Japan's Hydrogen-Powered Vehicle Research

Japan, a primary in automotive innovation, contender in investing in hydrogen-powered vehicles. Here's how this fact will impact car registrations and why it's essential to take into account:

Hydrogen-Powered Vehicles:

Japan's promise to sustainable and non-emission transportation extends beyond electric vehicles (EVs).

Hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FCVs) have gained fame due to their environmental benefits:

Zero tailpipe emissions.

Longer driving range compared to battery EVs.

Quick refueling times.

The study presumes that Hydrogen powered vehicles are the reason why Japan has not put up in the growth of Electric Vehicles and Hydrogen vehicles in the future such as the Toyota Mirai will be a strong contender for an alternative fuel to Internal combustion engine and to Electric vehicles. (Lopez Jaramillo et al., 2019, p. conclusion)

Toyota's Leading Role:

Toyota: a Japanese automotive leader, has been at the lead of hydrogen-powered vehicle development.

This flagship FCV, the Toyota Mirai, iterates their belief to this technology.

Toyota's extensive infrastructure to hydrogen refueling stations further supports FCV adoption.

Impact on Car Registrations in Japan and thus a competitor

Japan's emphasizing on hydrogen-powered vehicles may have differentiate car registrations:

Decreased Production of Traditional Combustion Engine Vehicles and electric vehicles : As resources shift toward FCVs, traditional gasoline, diesel vehicle production and also electric vehicles may have declined.

Increased FCV Registrations: Purchase of hydrogen-powered vehicles, including the Mirai, likely will be forefront.

Customer adoption and Perception: Public awareness of FCVs may have grown, improving consumer choice.

Presumed Breakthrough:

While it remains a assumption, Japan's dedication to FCVs suggests a future breakthrough.

Toyota's ongoing research and designing with other leaders could lead to improvement in hydrogen technology.

A improvement might involve improving efficiency, cost reduction, or infrastructure expansion such as Hydrogen fuel charging station

In short, Japan's strategic gamble in hydrogen-powered vehicles, coupled with Toyota's pivotal role, shapes the Japan's of car registrations landscape. As the industry grows, we anticipate new innovative developments in the realm of hydrogen mobility.

China's Electric Vehicle Registrations and Peak Consumption

China, a global leader in EV registration, has experienced remarkable growth in EV purchases. However, recent statics suggest a future slowdown. Several reasons contribute to this change:

Primarily, market saturation and peaked consumption is reason a important role. China's EV market has peaked, boasting a substantial base of existing EV owners. As the market realises saturation, new registrations are naturally withered off. Early adopters may already purchased EVs, leading to less demand among this consumers.

Further, organizational changes and subsidy reductions impact registration rates. At first, China incentivized EV adoption through great subsidies. In following years, the government has slowly scaled back these financial incentives to make sure market sustainability. Which resulted, the reduced allure of subsidies may be the reason to slower growth in registrations. Infrastructure challenges exist. Despite substantial increase, China struggles with EV infrastructure limits. Reasoning such as charging station availability and range anxiety affect consumer belief. These reasons and concerns influence registration decision making. Economic factors come into suggests. China's economic growth has struggled, affecting overall consumer growth. While EVs remain exciting, they represent an important investment. Economic risks may prompt future buyers to refactor their options. Lastly, environmental concerns and policy shifts shape the platform. China remains promised to environmental sustainability. However, the sight is shifting from mere quantity to quality. Stricter emissions standards also a push for higher-quality EVs may factor in registration numbers. In summary, China's EV market has a complex interlaying of factors, from market maturity and policy changes to infrastructure being built and economic growth. These dynamics collectively will be a reason to the observed decline in EV registrations.(Yanmei Li, Ningning Ha, n.d.)

Conclusion:

Summarizing the study, the emergence of electric mobility marks a very important transformational change in the industry within the automotive sector and broader transportation ecosystem. The increase in electric vehicle purchase implies not merely a trend but a significant and substantial shift in the market driven by a plethora of reasons. Technological advancements, visibly in the battery technology, have been one of the most important factor in making Electric vehicles more affordable to the larger masses and also something to sort for the customer. (Krishna, 2021, sec. 4.1) These innovations led to better battery efficiency and performance, increased driving ranges and reduced costs, thereby fostering greater acceptance of electric vehicles among consumers. (Buhmann & Criado, 2023, sec. 2.2.2). The index made proves these above points

Over and above these factors mentioned above earlier, several other factors also contribute to the evolving landscape of electric mobility and it impacts for the transportation landscape.

Technological innovation: More than advancements in battery technology, ongoing innovations in electric vehicles design, materials and manufacturing process are driving performance, better efficiency and also customers can buy it more cheaply. For example, the upgradation of lightweight material, more aerodynamic way of constructing the car and better efficiency in electric drivetrains are in many ways driving the overall enhancement and range of the vehicles such as may b in the case in the future when it comes to solid state batteries and wireless charging systems which may unveil the potential to innovate the electric vehicle market by offering faster charging times, lesser range anxiety and better overall performance, such as in case of Japan and incase of China

Betterment in the infrastructure: The more adoption of charging infrastructure is an important factor for the widespread consumer behavior of purchase in electric vehicles. Governments, utilities and private companies are investing heavily in building charging networks to address range anxiety and facilitate long distance travel. Beyond that innovation in smart grid technology and vehicle to grid (V2G) integration enable bidirectional energy flow between electric vehicle and the grid, this allows electric vehicles to provide as a grid storage mechanism device and also can integrate and enhance renewable energy implementation. So the Growth market in Western countries seem stable.

Everchanging and dynamic ecosystem: The electric vehicle market is innovating rapidly, which is also shifting consumer preferences, regulatory mandates and market competition. Automakers increase investing in electric vehicles research and production thus capitalizing on the demand growth and such compliance will help in better implementation of emission regulation. This further resulting in better electric vehicle models and thereby increasing more range of options to consumer in many vehicle criteria and various other price points. The growth of this table in most countries all seem to go only upward including the world for the above reason and as per the predictive index.

In broad context the transition of electric mobility can be seen as a multi-faceted and very unsolvable complex transformation which also include technological, economic, regulatory and social dimensions. When these challenges are addressed and opportunities are seemed the inherent trend in the change, stakeholders can make it faster the change towards a more eco-friendly and efficient transportation mechanism. Thus, index proves that will be the future other than exceptions.

The future moreover, will be regarding concern of sustainable environment and reduce climate change have sort the governments all over the world to immediately prescribe laws and policies which reduces emissions from the automobiles. Electric vehicles considered to be emission free during running, have been seen as an important solution in this trend. Incentives and tax subsidies, rebates and other benefits have been very nurturing factor for consumers to lean more towards this and the governments recognizing it will be an opportunity in a strategic manner to provide better energy security and less shortage gaining a better sight in the world markets especially in Germany.

All these factors should not discount the fact even more steps are to be further taken in order to make it faster the transition to electric vehicles. Range anxiety, which is a raised due to the factor of limited energy in a battery when compared to Internal combustion engine cars and still better and more infrastructure for electric charging stations need to be addressed and thus the continuous deter some consumers from taking up electric vehicles. Facing range anxiety will require more investment in charging infrastructure along with innovative battery technology to better the driving ranges and thus also reduce hours spend at a charging station. Which might constrain in USA. As per index.

Also to be taken into consideration as per the study is that the initial purchase price of an electric vehicle is a primary disadvantage still to consumer, no matter the long-term cost savings associated with better fuel and less maintenance costs. Regulators can further play an important role in making electric vehicles more in hands of consumers by offering subsidies or incentives and supporting more research and development in the future. In addition to all this awareness and educating the consumers regarding the advantages of electric vehicles plays an important in reducing misconceptions and providing a greater acceptance.

The change from internal combustion engine to electric mobility presents itself as an important opportunity to mitigate emissions, improve air quality and enhance energy security. These changes if addressing key challenges such as range anxiety, affordability and awareness to consumers, stakeholders will accelerate the taking up of electric vehicles and thus provide a way to better sustainable future in transportation.

The above study with Machine learning and manual calculation finds that other than Japan and China all the rest of the world is seem to be in a growth stage and will follow suit worldwide and in the coming future India will also seem to be a major player in the Electric Vehicle market.

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It is estimated that the revenue in the Electric Vehicles market will increase at a CAGR⁽¹⁾ of 23.2% from 2016 to 2028

Revenue

Revenue forecast in billion US\$

Notes: (1) CAGR: Compound Annual Growth Rate
Sources: Statista Market Insights, 2023

Appendix fig 2 Source: Statista (Adebayo Oluwatobi Kazeem, n.d.-b)

With a revenue of US\$188.7 billion, China had the biggest market among selected countries in 2022

Revenue

Revenue forecast in billion US\$

26 Notes: (1) CAGR: Compound Annual Growth Rate

Sources: Statista Market Insights, 2023

Appendix 3

Code used in Azure Machine Learning via Python Framework for uploading historical data by ZSW

```
import mtable
```

```
paths = [{'file': './train_data/timeseries_train.csv'}]
```

```
train_table = mtable.from_delimited_files(paths)
```